

EXECHIOPSIS (EXECHIOPSIS S. STR.) PATULA PLASSMANN, 1978
(DIPTERA, MYCETOPHILIDAE)
– THE FIRST RECORD IN THE CZECH REPUBLIC

EXECHIOPSIS (EXECHIOPSIS S. STR.) PATULA PLASSMANN, 1978
(DIPTERA, MYCETOPHILIDAE)
– PIERWSZE STWIERDZENIE W REPUBLICIE CZESKIEJ

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ABSTRACT: Two caves and a corridor in a limestone quarry were visited in the Czech Karst Protected Area for the preliminary study of their cave parietal fauna, mainly Diptera in 1999, 2001 and 2004, during autumn and winter. *Exechiopsis patula* PLASSMANN, 1978 was discovered for the first time in the Czech Republic. Besides it, 11 species of other Diptera were recorded in this underground environment.

KEY WORDS: *Exechiopsis patula*, Diptera, the first record, caves, parietal fauna, Czech Republic

INTRODUCTION

The family Mycetophilidae is a very well studied group of Diptera in the Czech Republic. The last checklist of Diptera for the Czech and Slovak Republics (ŠEVČÍK & KOŠEL 2009) contains 542 species in the Czech Republic. In spite of this fact, there are many rare species which can be discovered only by a chance. Such a rare species in the Czech Republic seems to be *Exechiopsis patula* PLASSMANN, 1978. As to the research of Diptera in Czech caves, there is so far only a publication of CZIŽEK (1916) from the Moravian Karst. Besides the caves of Moravian Karst their research is generally insufficient.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Two caves and a corridor in a limestone quarry were visited in the Czech Karst Protected Landscape Area (P.L.A.) in 1999, 2001 and 2004 and at this opportunity parietal fauna including Diptera was collected. The material was collected from cave walls by an aspirator and preserved in 75% alcohol. All the material was collected by the author (V. KOŠEL).

RESULTS

Three underground sites were visited:

1. Jeskyně nad vodopády cave, 309 m a.s.l., 10 m long, without aphotic zone, visited 15.9.1999 and 7.11.1999.

2. Foxova štola gallery in the limestone quarry, the main corridor cca 153 m long with several short branches, visited 27.4.2001 and 15.2.2004. The main gallery was explored in its entirety. The temperature in the main corridor (15.2.2004): the entrance 3,2° C, at the 50th m 6,5° C, at the end (cca 153 m) 8,2° C. The main corridor has a disphotic regime up to the end.

3. Barrandova jeskyně cave, 251 m a.s.l., 366 m long, 44 m deep, visited 13.10.2004. Only the upper horizontal corridor with a length of 30 m with two entrances, and with an euphotic regime was explored. Due to the orientation of the cave to the south, the corridor is warm and dry.

E. patula PLASSMANN, 1978, one male was found in the Jeskyně nad vodopády cave, on the cave wall, 7.11.1999. The species was described by PLASSMANN (1978) according to a single male from Swedish Lapland. The second record comes from Switzerland (CHANDLER 1998). The more precise data on its occurrence in Switzerland were provided to me by P.J. CHANDLER (*in litt.*): Graubunden, Zernez, 1 male, 15.-18, viii, 1978, altitude 1450 m, leg. G. BÄCHLI. Numerous findings are known from Norway (SØLI & KJÆRANDSEN 2008). In Slovakia it was discovered in great numbers in three caves in the Belianske Tatry Mts (890 – 1390 m a.s.l.) (KOŠEL 2004).

As PLASSMANN's figures of male genitalia are very schematic and females have probably not been known at all, I decided to add to this article more detailed figures of the terminalia of both sexes (Figs 1 - 3). The figures were drawn according to the specimens from the Suchá diera cave (1183 m a.s.l.) in the Javorová dolina valley in the Vysoké Tatry Mts. This cave is the 4th site with its occurrence in Slovakia. 1681 specimens (1046♂♂, 635♀♀) originate from this single site (5 winter seasons, 2003 – 2007) (*unpublished*). The Czech Republic is the 5th country with this species in Europe.

Other Diptera from this cave: at the first visit (15.9.1999) there was no dipteran fauna found.

A following visit to this cave on 7.11.1999 yielded Diptera as follows:

Culicidae:	<i>Culex pipiens</i> LINNAEUS, 1758	30♀♀
	<i>Culiseta glaphyroptera</i> (SCHINER, 1864)	8♀♀
Mycetophilidae:	<i>Rymosia fasciata</i> (MEIGEN, 1804)	6♂♂ 5♀♀
	<i>Exechia dizona</i> EDWARDS, 1924	6♂♂
	<i>Exechia exigua</i> LUNDSTRÖM, 1909	3♂♂
	<i>Exechiopsis patula</i> PLASSMANN, 1978	1♂
Drosophilidae:	<i>Drosophila kuntzei</i> DUDA, 1924	2♀♀

2. Foxova štola gallery (27.4.2001 and 15.2.2004)

		27.4.2001	15.2.2004
Culicidae:	<i>Culex pipiens</i> LINNAEUS, 1758	2♀♀	55♀♀
	<i>Culiseta glaphyroptera</i> (SCHINER, 1864)		1♀
Mycetophilidae:	<i>Exechiopsis lackschewitziana</i> (STACKELBERG, 1948)		1♂2♀♀
	<i>Rymosia fasciata</i> (MEIGEN, 1804)	1♀	
	<i>Tarnania fenestralis</i> (MEIGEN, 1838)	9♂♂ 12♀♀	
Heleomyzidae:	<i>Scoliocentra villosa</i> (MEIGEN, 1830)		1♂1♀

3. Barrandova jeskyně cave (13.10.2004)

Culicidae	<i>Culex pipiens</i> LINNAEUS, 1758	1♂ 87♀♀
	<i>Culiseta annulata</i> (SCHRANK, 1776)	2♀♀
Mycetophilidae:	<i>Rymosia fasciata</i> (MEIGEN, 1804)	1♀
Heleomyzidae:	<i>Heteromyza atricornis</i> MEIGEN, 1830	5♀♀

The record of *Heteromyza atricornis* had been published from here by KOŠEL *et al.* (2006) as one of the first records in the Czech Republic.

FIGS. 1-2. *Exechiopsis patula* PLASSMANN, 1978, ♂. 1. Terminalia, ventral view. 2. Gonostylus, dorsal view of the left part.

DISCUSSION

Dipterans have been explored rarely in the Czech caves. The oldest and the most detailed research of this group was made in the caves of the Moravský kras - Moravian Karst (now The Protected Landscape Area Moravian Karst) by CZIŽEK (1916). Since then, no thorough research of Diptera in Czech caves has been made. The number of caves in the Czech Karst P.L.A. reaches the hundreds and this territory calls for more thorough research, at least at the level of its species spectrum.

Compared to other karst regions of the Czech Republic. (Moravian Karst) and Slovakia, the dipteran fauna in caves of the Czech Karst (12 species) seems to be much poorer with regard to the quality and quantity. The reason for this fact is that only a low number of caves have been explored and also the frequency of visits has been low.

FIG. 3. *Exechiopsis patula* PLASSMANN, 1978, ♀. Terminalia, lateral view.

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REFERENCES

- CHANDLER P. J. 1998: 20. Mycetophilidae. Pp. 113-125. [In:] MERZ B., BÄCHLI J., HAENNI J.-P., GONSETH Y. (EDS.): Fauna Helvetica 1. Diptera - Checklist. 365 pp.
- CZIŽEK K. 1916: Beiträge zur rezenten Fauna der mährischen Höhlen (I. Teil). Zeitschrift des mährischen Landesmuseum, 15: 13-58.
- KOŠEL V. 2004: Parietal Diptera in caves of the Belianske Tatry Mts. (Slovakia, The Western Carpathians). I. Introduction and species spectrum. Acta facultatis Ecologiae, Zvolen **12**: 69-73.
- KOŠEL V., DVOŘÁKOVÁ K., MARTINEK V. 2006: Faunistic records: Heleomyzidae. *Thelida atricornis* MEIGEN, 1830. Dipterologica Bohemoslovaca 13. Acta Univ. Carolinae - Biologica **50**(1-2): 155.
- PLASSMANN E., 1978: Neue Pilzmücken aus Schweden und Bulgarien (Insecta: Diptera: Mycetophilidae). Senckenbergiana biologica **58**: 205-214.
- SØLI G., KJÆRANSEN J. 2008: Additions to the Norwegian fauna of fungus gnats (Diptera, Mycetophilidae). Norwegian Journal of Entomology **55**: 31-41.
- ŠEVČÍK J., KOŠEL V. 2009: Mycetophilidae Newman, 1834. [In:] JEDLIČKA L., KÚDELA M. & STLOUKALOVÁ V. (EDS.): Checklist of Diptera of the Czech Republic and Slovakia. Electronic version 2. <<http://zoology.fns.uniba.sk/diptera2009>> + CD-ROM: ISBN 978-80-969629-4-5.